

Role of E-Commerce for Vietnamese Enterprises in the Global Background

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Abstract:

The objective of the paper is to assess the state of digital business with Vietnamese businesses. To accomplish this goal, we conduct an overview of documents related to digital business and e-commerce, then we analyze the current situation of Vietnamese businesses in the context of digital and revolutionary business. industry 4.0. Based on the results of the digital business and e-commerce of Vietnamese businesses, we conduct opportunities and challenges analysis, from which we propose solutions to help Vietnamese businesses operate. Better action in the context of globalization.

Keywords: Vietnamese businesses, digital business, e-commerce.

1. Introduction

Since the advent of the internet, the world has been undeniably important in all areas of social life. It can be said that today the world of e-commerce is growing strongly, it is an integral part of the operation of the business. In terms of scale, with a low starting point of about 4 billion USD in 2015, but thanks to the average growth rate for 3 consecutive years, the scale of the e-commerce market in 2019 is about more than 10 billion USD. If the growth rate of 2020 continues to be at 30%, by 2020 the market size will reach 13 billion USD. This scale will be larger than the goal stated in the Master Plan for e-commerce development in the 2016-2020 period, according to this goal, the scale of retail e-commerce (B2C) will reach 10 billion USD by 2020.

With such a fast and stable growth, combined with the trend of shifting consumer shopping habits, it can be confirmed that e-commerce will increasingly occupy more important positions for businesses. Karma.

2. Research overview

The basis for businesses to deploy digital business is digital technologies, which are mainly 4.0 technologies, but Industry 4.0 technology has only been recognized since 2012, so the in-depth study of this field, or the transfer model change the numberless.

2.1. E-commerce, digital business

Many businesses are racing to create the highest competitive advantage, while others simply try to catch up with their competitors with new e-commerce strategies. The main trends of e-commerce in the near future are:

a. Multi-channel Selling

The multi-channel sales trend allows businesses to reach their customers on a variety of platforms and environments, from online to offline. As users increasingly demand higher experience and convenience of services, Multi-channel Selling will certainly be a prominent trend in the coming period.

The increasing trend of online shopping through social networking sites is unquestionable, because we spend a lot of time on social networks and are influenced by product information, advertising such as Facebook, , Instagram or Zalo. This trend has led to a sharp increase in transactions and online purchases via social networks.

b. Payment on delivery is still a common payment method (COD)

E-commerce infrastructure provides consumers with many payment options: Payment via bank, payment on delivery, payment by e-wallet ... However, in Vietnam, the form of payment upon delivery COD is still the

main payment method, accounting for 75% of transactions. The reason is that the habit of using cash and this method creates a safer feeling for consumers, helping them to avoid the risk of losing goods, defective goods or not receiving the right quality goods from the seller.

But this is one of the biggest problems hindering the development of the e-commerce market in Vietnam. To develop non-cash payments, it is necessary to closely manage the quality of goods on online sales sites, in order to create consumer confidence. The authorities must operate effectively, there must be strict sanctions against the seller in order to protect the buyer.

c. Speed up delivery and improve customer experience (Customer Experience)

It can be seen that consumers have never played a central role and have an important voice in the digital economy today. Every user experience, reviews, positive or negative feedback has a strong influence on the business performance of e-commerce businesses, especially when the Vietnamese market is witnessing fierce competition. from many big brands.

Except for digitized products, items still have to be shipped directly. Clearly, as e-commerce thrives, delivery needs to be improved even faster.

With the eagerness to receive a new purchase, everyone wants to receive the goods soon. This is also a very important factor that helps e-commerce compete with traditional commerce: Improve delivery speed or lose sales. In the coming years, intraday delivery is probably the most awaited trend.

d. Virtual assistants (Chatbot, AI)

The technology market changes so quickly, Chatbot or AI has really penetrated and is used effectively by businesses. According to Chatbot Magazine, 25% of customer care services will be integrated with AI virtual assistant in 2020. While research conducted in 2018, 34% of customers feel comfortable communicating with Chatbot when buying.

Although still quite awkward, chatbots are continuously being improved and are expected to become a marketing trend in business and e-commerce websites next year. In fact, chatbots will be the first point of contact between customers and an automated system built with AI.

Customer care chatbots will become more and more "human", leading customers through a smoother buying journey. However, if done not carefully, chatbots will harm the business.

e. Smartphone application software (Mobile Apps)

With the development of the Internet, 4G-5G and mobile devices, especially smartphones and electronic payment methods are widely used. Therefore, the trend of e-commerce on mobile platforms via application software is indispensable. This is also what happened in developed countries that came before.

Mobile Apps are a trend used to buy online from users. However, businesses are still confused and do not understand the standards on mobile to meet customers and increase conversion rates for purchases.

2.2. Characteristics of e-commerce

No template for the e-commerce model: There is no best way to apply e-commerce for all businesses. You must rely on the characteristics of your business, products and services to create an e-commerce model that's right for you. And remember one important thing: the key to your e-commerce success lies in the phrase "create your own identity".

Fierce competition: The cost to implement e-commerce is very low so almost anyone can apply e-commerce, leading to fierce competition in this field. Therefore, to be successful, you must know how to invest: pay attention to network marketing, utilities and quality of customer service, creating your own characteristics. Do these 3 elements well and you will succeed

The rapid pace of innovation: IT is an area where technological backwardness takes place very fast. e-commerce is a type of business based on the development of IT, so the pace of innovation also takes place very fast, requiring businesses to participate in e-commerce to be always innovating: technological innovation, innovate business methods, innovate thinking, innovate management ... If you are slow in this innovation, you must review your ability to succeed when applying e-commerce.

2.3. Benefits of e-commerce

Facing the great benefits and popularity of e-commerce, e-commerce has now become an important tool for every business in its business. Benefits that e-commerce brings to businesses include:

- Promote and market information to the global market at a low cost: with today's internet connectivity, you can easily deliver advertising information to millions of people from all over the world. Depending on the needs and financial ability to pay for the promotion, businesses need to have an appropriate advertising plan.

- Better service for customers: With e-commerce, you can provide catalogs, information, detailed price lists to customers quickly and conveniently, and online shopping has become easily disseminate so much ... In this day and age, digital life has pushed up the pace of life, customers increasingly require everything to be faster from product information, purchases, payments and the main. After-sales books, ...

- Increase sales: With e-commerce, your customers now no longer have limitations on geographical distance or working time. Therefore, each business reaches a large number of customers, increasing its revenue and profit.

- Reduce costs: With e-commerce, it will not cost too much for renting stores, premises, waiters, ... Especially for export businesses, the costs incurred due to the distance may significantly be reduced.

- Competitive advantage: In the context that most businesses are currently involved in e-commerce, businesses with innovative ideas, good marketing strategies will be advantageous to compete. Because e-commerce is a playground for creativity and innovation for all businesses.

In short, the e-commerce market is really an opportunity for Vietnamese businesses. Businesses don't think it's too early to talk about e-commerce. The winners are often the pioneer, moreover, businesses have started to pay much attention to e-commerce, so to take advantage, your business cannot afford to take a walk and observe other people taking action, but your business must act quickly.

3. Enterprises in developing countries are not high with digital business in the era of globalization

Digital business - the mandatory development path of businesses in developed countries is not high, going deep into integration

Digital business is a form of business based on the application of advances in information technology and digital technology, in order to improve the efficiency of business operations. In the era of globalization, when Industry 4.0 has spread, businesses in developed countries are not required to gradually develop this type of business, because digital business: (i) Develop since 1984 with the website wibeside The first e-commerce, booming since the mid-1990s in developed countries, is now spreading thanks to Industry 4.0 globally. Promoting the primacy of Information Civilization, demonstrating the power of Knowledge Economy, which is the main activity in the digital economy, should be the main business activity of the future. (ii) Changing the business models in the world, from support to encroachment, has now moved to dominate the traditional economy. Digital technologies make business more convenient, space-free, time-independent, linking the real world to the virtual world, allowing people to participate and control the value chain. (iii) Help businesses transition to smart businesses, thanks to applications such as automation and supply chain documentation, e-banking systems, shopping, tracking and online payment. .. Help businesses lower prices, increase business success, when global competition is increasingly fierce, marginal profits are very small. (iv) Help businesses exchange data, coordinate quickly, effectively, and facilitate negotiation and implementation of contracts,

transactions and payments. As the preeminent interface for approaching and dealing with customers, when the number of objects using the internet and mobile devices is increasing and expanding according to the technology of universal connectivity ... (v) Helping enterprises to have a part in the "pie" of transactions, supervising the circulation, payment for goods traded worth over the US \$ 50,000 billion. Help businesses in low-developed countries "leapfrog" in the global economic game, benefit from Industry 4.0 with the world's leading businesses. In order not to be left behind, all businesses must be proactive and urgently involved, but firstly build and develop an ecosystem for digital business.

The components that govern digital business capabilities and limit the power of digital business

Joining is easy, but bringing digital business into regular operation, bringing high efficiency, and avoiding operational risks is not easy, because in order to do so, businesses need to develop synchronously on: (i) Technology infrastructure for deploying appropriate, necessary and not too obsolete technologies to be able to install and operate modern applications. Should not be too large in terms of capacity, too advanced in technology so that it is not used up, not used, causing waste in terms of investment, energy, maintenance costs ... (ii) Intellectual properties, such as technology, software, patent invention to conduct business, according to the characteristics of the business. No copyright infringement, high enough quality to compete, and strong enough to prevent data theft, information leakage. (iii) Qualified employees to operate and exploit existing technologies and equipment, effectively, promptly and effectively serve the business. In addition to investing in improving technology and foreign languages, it is also necessary to increase remuneration, so as not to cause material temptation, but to cause immeasurable losses for businesses. (iv) Leaders, in charge of areas capable of directing and supervising digital business activities, of making final decisions accurately and clearly, not being seduced or exploited by employees. This is a big bottleneck in underdeveloped countries, when business leaders, major shareholders often have limited IT and foreign language skills, reconciling this conflict is not easy. (v) Compatibility in digital business, especially in terms of game style, rules, and discipline between businesses and partners, the community and society. Many issues, such as upgrading infrastructure outside the enterprise; regulations and sanctions; commitments in free trade agreements (FTAs) ... are beyond the reach of businesses. Because each element governs the power of digital business, and that power of the business is usually limited to the least developed element. Therefore, to promote digital business, businesses need to be timely and realistic to invest synchronously, so as not to be left behind, but do not be deluded or wasted, but can also bring about many opportunities. festival.

Business development opportunities of enterprises in developed countries are not high, in an era of globalization, under the impact of Industry 4.0.

Businesses in developed countries are not high in the era of globalization, with existing and upcoming 4.0 technologies, there are many opportunities to develop digital businesses, because of the ability to meet the needs: (i) Gender Introduce and recommend needs to other businesses, supply chains, investors, customers and others, for an overview of the business. Digital business opportunities will come to businesses, when there are partners who follow the principle of "trading with friends and selling with wards", but can only cooperate to benefit through digital technology. (ii) Survey and find market information, from technology, equipment, to current and need-to-produce products, replaceable products, and product requirements according to a market segment. Helping businesses re-plan development strategies; restructuring of equipment, technology, human resources, products and customers and improving product quality, following development trends and economic contracts, under FTAs. (iii) Find customers, markets, partners and strategic partners, new technologies to maintain and expand the business, support restructuring and business development. Help businesses evaluate, select and evaluate business plans; supervising cash flows and goods flow; aggregate and analyze the deals to adjust the model, gradually shift to business intelligence. (iv) Linking workshops to form the optimal production cycle, linking with related businesses to improve supply chain quality, especially in the export business and collaborating with foreign direct investment (FDI) enterprises and foreign enterprises to "sneak" into the alleys and niches of supply chains, global value chains, to replace businesses that have been "turned

out". "From a broken supply chain. (v) Introduce traditional manufacturing industries, such as agriculture, tourism, education and health, into high technology, deploy and monitor new types of the economy such as sharing economy, night economy. Help businesses lower costs, improve competitiveness, participate in integrated socio-economic programs, together promote and complete the country's development process

Challenges in developing digital business of enterprises in developed countries are not high in the era of globalization, under the impact of Industry 4.0.

Mixed with opportunities is a challenge, in which the main challenges are: (i) Investment capital is insufficient and weak on high-end production factors, such as modern digital information infrastructure, professionals experts and specialized research institutes (Porter, 2012, p. 154). The capital required to purchase equipment, hire employees to operate efficiently beyond the capacity of the enterprise, or the expected profit increase is not commensurate with the investment. (ii) The legal corridor and information security in digital business, because in the low developed countries, there are always many ecological barriers for the digital economy from the state, many gaps for commercial fraud. trade. If civil business instability is criminalized; economic disputes that are not handled strictly, causing losses, damages, and leaked information - are easy to bring many businesses to the forefront. (iii) Number and quality of the personnel involved, the most influential is that officials in the "0.4" category only knowledgeable about information technology, always fear subordinates cheating, "overtaking". Or businesses do not have enough manpower to exploit equipment, applications and copyrights invested; or the person in charge has only a limited level, so the partner takes advantage of, causing damage. (iv) Business administration when conducting digital business, job placement and remuneration for the redundant labor sector due to technology elimination, especially the leaders, "the god". The digital business also makes it difficult for businesses that are familiar with relying on the umbrella of umbrellas to easily disclose and leave traces of unofficial expenses. metamorphosis. (v) Operational risks when enterprises use faulty software, equipment with a backdoor, pre-installed spyware, leak information when repairing equipment. Ethical risks lurking, when important documents are easily copied and stolen by corrupt employees, being bribed by rivals; risks of negligence, hacker attacks

International experience in developing digital business in businesses in an era of globalization

In addition to common experiences such as focusing on education and training, digital infrastructure development, e-commerce, e-government; The countries where businesses have developed digital businesses also have their own experience, can learn. Specifically: (i) Singapore soon has a clear and narrow development strategy: becoming the leading financial center in the region. Convenient economic activities, thanks to the success in teaching and learning foreign languages; promote publicity and transparency; good at attracting talents and resources from abroad. Recently, focusing on developing a fiber-optic network, 4G connectivity, building a smart country, expanding POS payment, taking information technology - communication as the foundation. (ii) The Korean Government always has a foresight, soon force domestic businesses to associate and continuously innovate despite success. Since 1980 started the construction of e-Government, in 1995-2002, it completed the framework law on information and online services. Since 2003, the application of a uniform digital standard has recently allowed the diversification of online software, in order to promote competition and catch up with world technology. (iii) China takes advantage of its large local market, a dynamic young population, and competition for digital ecosystems to diversify and develop a broad digital economy. There are flexible legal provisions that encourage innovation, create conditions and space for digital businesses to experiment, both as investors and consumers of digital technologies. Encourage online activities, especially commerce, banking and electronic payments (CIEM, 2018b); is trying to develop a 5G network to become a smart country, with the "Made in China 2025" Program. (iv) Israel uses digital business to promote entrepreneurship, with a tearing mindset, watching creative responsibility as living energy, creating "miraculous" changes when applying digital business. Based on the vision of elites, macro institutions,

implementation strategies, and action together, 4.0 technologies have contributed to turning Israel into a "Startup Country". Focus on developing high-tech agriculture, using a vision to replace experience, making the country strongly affected by desertification, becoming a major supplier of agricultural products to the EU (Le Quoc Anh & Le Thi Tram Anh, 2019)

4. The reality of digital business in Vietnam

Business activities of businesses in Vietnam began to bloom in the late 1990s when computers were widely equipped, businesses scrambled to set up domain names, according to the spread of the internet. Strongly develop following the development of enterprises after the 2005 Enterprise Law, and especially after 2007, when Vietnam joined the World Trade Organization. Over the past 10 years, it has been growing steadily both in quantity, quality and achievements. In the area specializing in digital business, in 2016, there were 11,155 businesses in information technology and communication services alone. Concentrating in the fields related to computers and telecommunications, creating jobs for nearly 233,000 employees, accounting for 1.66% of the national labor force (VCCI, 2018, p.79). In 2017, the number of businesses in this sector increased to 12,182, creating a growth rate of 9.2%, the strongest growth was Postage. As of June 15, 2019, there were 440 postal businesses, with 423 active businesses, in the first 6 months of 2019, the revenue was estimated at 13,560 billion VND, contributing to the budget of 362 billion VND (Lan Phuong, 2019). Forming many "pillars" with great potential and strong growth, such as Viettel Group, FPT Group, MISA Joint Stock Company, CMC Company, VNG Joint Stock Company. Along with 48 other leading information technology enterprises in 2018, with revenue in 2017 equivalent to 16.69 billion USD, the number of employees is 92,795 people - accounting for 35.5% of revenue and 22.9% of total manpower The whole sector (Hong Duyen, 2018). E-commerce has become a popular activity, thanks to the number of internet users in 2016 that exceeded 64 million, approximately 67% of the population, ranked 13th in the world, with many strong e-commerce sites.

In 2017, 61% of businesses equipped mobile devices for business; 85% use financial accounting software; 28% use customer relationship software; 22% use supply management software (VCCI, 2018, p.85) Transport enterprises use FastGo, Be, VATO to compete with Grab, Uber. The tourism industry has many Vietnamese startups such as My tour, Luxstay. competing with big names like Booking, Agoda or AirB & B. In general, the advantages of young and dynamic human resources have been exploited; Catch up the trend when using technologies: artificial intelligence, internet of things, big data, blockchains; e-commerce has spread to mobile devices as well. Attracting a lot of investment, in 2017 alone, there were 21 startups in the e-commerce field receiving 83 million USD of FDI, the highest in all industries in general

Digital business of Vietnamese enterprises is still limited and weak

Impressive starters, the digital business activities of Vietnamese enterprises are still limited and weak, typically: (i) The number of businesses participating in digital business is not much, although the telecommunications infrastructure is quite synchronized, mobile coverage reached 99.7% of the population, of which 3G and 4G coverage reached over 98% with low rates (Anh Minh, 2019). The number of businesses specializing in new digital businesses accounts for 2.2% of the total number of businesses, mostly young businesses, with small capital, brand value and competitiveness are still low. (ii) Non-professional enterprises are not interested in digital business, many businesses are still passive, their access capacity, applicability and development of modern technology are still low. Making digital business activities often arbitrary, heavy spontaneity, efficiency is not attractive enough, many business leaders do not have faith in digital business. (iii) The majority of Vietnamese enterprises currently use outdated technology, mostly 2.0 or lower, only 6.6% of enterprises have enough resources to completely switch from old technology to new technology (Le Quoc). Et al, 2018b). On the other hand, during the period 2007-2014, macroeconomic instability, business capital and human resources were often devoted to traditional business activities, not much "land" for digital business activities. (iv) The

digital economy has a small scale, the scale of e-commerce has reached only US \$ 5.2 billion, the beneficiaries are mainly in the FDI sector, even large state-owned enterprises only earn profits. preparations. Making the motivation for digital business development is still low, having a tough management agency, machines taking advantage of the obscurity of the law, making it difficult for businesses to pioneer. (v) The struggle with criminals, ensuring cybersecurity is still challenging, making the market confidence in digital business decline, the risk of risks always covering, even though Vietnamese people love and love to use. technology. On the other hand, the business relationship between Vietnamese enterprises is inherently unsustainable, many frauds, when there are problems, the law is not strict, causing concern for businesses when doing business in the virtual market

The cause of the limitations and weaknesses in the digital business of the business

There are many, with the main causes are: (i) Awareness on many aspects of our country, especially in the economy, there are many differences, often backward compared to the world, in which the perception of digital business is still inadequacies. The stalemate of thinking makes the inertia in traditional big business, the organization and development of digital business for businesses difficult and lack of support, especially from the state. (ii) Vietnam has a slow digital strategy development, because this term appeared only in the Party's document on September 27, 2019, in Resolution No. 52-NQ / TW. On the other hand, only focused on some areas such as digital agriculture, digital tourism ... - and the era of the Industrial Revolution 4.0 or the digital economy era in Vietnam is the paperwork, at the conference (Nguyen Dinh Cung) Minh Thai, 2018). (iii) Enterprises themselves are not favorable, because of the small scale, about 68% work in the service sector, mainly in small businesses, catering services, motorbike repair services - no need for development.

Processing enterprises are more inclined to outsourcing and assembling, just "taking jobs" from their partners, being passive in transactions, and needing little innovation, if the number of added value businesses is not large. (iv) The digital business platform of the enterprise is not synchronized, temporarily stable on "hard" infrastructure; Inadequate facilities, data quality and accessibility. Data is weak, lacking, dispersed, low reliability because many ministries "spontaneously and independently" data (Truong Son, 2015), are less shared and difficult to connect, and the copyright is often violated. (v) There are many other barriers, the most obstacle is the economic management apparatus, not having the necessary independence, many internal limitations, not encouraging but always making it difficult for businesses (Le Quoc Anh). & Le Thi Tram Anh, 2017). Many "harsh, cruel administrative procedures" (Nguyen Sinh Hung, cited by Le Kien, 2016) and officials "0.4" are corrupt, risk of criminalizing stalking business, stealing business ideas. righteous businessman. In addition, there is a lack of coordination among ministries and agencies, people do not have the habit of online shopping, businesses have more concerns than the transformation of the digital economy .

Developing digital business - the responsibility of Vietnamese enterprises

The context of extensive integration under the impact of Industry 4.0, making digital business development a responsibility, is a vital condition for businesses in Vietnam, because only new digital businesses: (i) Hy hoping to bring profits to shareholders in the context of fierce global competition, Vietnam is integrating deeply with more than 50 leading partners in the world. Without digital business, it is difficult for businesses to find strategic partners, build relationships with customers, difficult to access resources, including bank credit, so it is no different from suicide. (ii) Do not fall behind, have the condition to exist in the market economy, because it allows rapid application and many new achievements of science and technology. Ensuring the integration of businesses, which can go hand in hand with other businesses in the sharing economy, thus having a certain position in supply chains, regional and global value chains. (iii) Mobilize and accompany with on-going processes, such as digital transformation, growth model transformation as a responsible entity ... Help businesses grow faster with their children roads must go, and at the same time contribute to turning Vietnam into a country with a modern economy. (iv) Overcoming the challenges of integration, resolving negative externalities, the negative side of the market economy, setting an example for start-up businesses. The

"cascades" of cheap, but detailed, high-quality, eco-friendly goods - flooding under FTAs, will drive away businesses that refuse to innovate. (v) Helping Vietnamese industries, regions and systems, creating high growth rates, when enterprises overcome inherent weaknesses in the capital, technology and marketing; to better exploit national advantages in deep integration. If not 5-7 years later, when FTAs are stable, Vietnamese enterprises will lose a rare opportunity, and there is a risk of being annexed or bankrupt (Le Quoc Anh & Le Thi Tram Anh, 2018a). , by the risk of destruction from Industry 4.0 (Tran Dinh Thien, quoted by Pham Tuyen, 2017).

Business development opportunities for businesses in Vietnam

Businesses in Vietnam have many opportunities to develop digital business, typically from: (i) The change in awareness of Industry 4.0, as reflected in Resolution No. 52-NQ / TW of the Ministry Politics on a number of guidelines and policies to actively participate in Industry 4.0. Removing the bladder, except for the former, now the Party determines that participating in Industry 4.0 is an indispensable requirement, an important and urgent strategic task - creating a golden opportunity for businesses to develop digital business. (ii) Practical Action The Government will follow Resolution No. 52-NQ / TW to promote digital transformation, with a focus on digital economy development. Prioritize the development of industries with high readiness, deploy nearly 20 programs of research, training, development and application of technology in development - greatly supporting the development of digital businesses of the enterprise. (iii) Much other assistance, such as increasingly open rules, increasingly diverse technology, proximity, lower implementation costs, increased support from the state and the community, and the number of people using equipment smart increasingly ... Training institutions increasingly provide the market of human resources trained, knowledgeable and more proficient in digital business, more suitable for each business. (iv) Spillover of digital business activities from strategic partners, customer businesses, supply chain enterprises, FDI enterprises and enterprises in FTAs ... Position in the supply chain , the value chain is a big push for Vietnamese businesses to promote a digital business because of their long-term and long-term benefits, when there are many limitations and weaknesses. (v) Regional and international economic fluctuations, as Vietnam increasingly engages in deeper development programs of the ASEAN Economic Community (AEC), or in the lower Mekong region, East-West economic corridor ... In addition, it is an opportunity to receive from the assistance of United Nations programs, international organizations, even from international instability such as trade war. The US-China, disrupting many supply chains, should encourage Vietnamese businesses to develop digital businesses to replace ...

5. Solutions to promote the development of digital business for businesses in Vietnam

Developing digital business for businesses is an urgent and unavoidable task; However, it is still only one of the key tasks that need to be done in order to raise Vietnam's socio-economic development. To make this development in the right direction, promote achievements, gradually overcome defects, exploit opportunities well, meet requirements in the context of globalization, under the impact of Industry 4.0, good service for General career, it is necessary to deploy the following solutions synchronously:

Firstly, gather the whole nation's intelligence to plan a "game" in the direction of unanimity and cooperation, for the sake of global and long-term interests in the integration posture, thereby indicating the role, position and responsibility. responsibilities and interests of enterprises, to outline development strategies.

In 1820, the size of Vietnam's economy was bigger than the Philippines and Myanmar combined, more than half that of Thailand, and the average income per capita was approximately, but now less than one-fifth of the world average (Bui Quang Vinh, according to VV Thành, 2016). Part of the reason is that, although 30 years of Doi Moi have brought about many important achievements, the doctrine of economic development still has some problems, many people have not been interested in revealing uniforms. To overcome the current lagging trend, it is possible to carry out a "catch up growth", a new "game" that needs to be unanimously united in order to develop existing capabilities, and take advantage of opportunities. festival. To do so, Vietnam needs a new development doctrine, consistent with the position of a new country with low average income, only 10 years of

journey to overcome the middle income trap, which is "playing" the economy with a powerful country. It must be a scientific and creative doctrine, it is best to crystallize the wisdom of the entire nation, consistent with reality and have a solid foundation (Le Quoc Anh & Le Thi Tram Anh, 2018b). The core of this new doctrine must be similar to those of economically active economies, the "creative" part of Vietnam does not make it different in the integrated playing community. On the other hand, it is a doctrine that helps our country integrate into Industry 4.0, so it is necessary to have revolutionary thinking, revolutionary decisions, directed by revolutionary people, according to revolutionary behavior. At that time, the new economic development would ensure the universal and long-term interests, all elements - including the business sector, could identify the right roles, positions and responsibilities; as well as benefits. Accordingly, enterprises in each industry, field, region, locality ... have just developed an appropriate and scientific development strategy to create healthy development in a common, unified and self-developed plan. I have developed and contributed the most to my common career.

Secondly, synchronously deploying solutions from institutional innovation, improving resource allocation, upgrading infrastructure, renewing equipment, technology, and transforming growth models, in order to develop business systems. strong national industry.

Developing a digital business is important, but having a strong national business system is even more important. Therefore, the business development strategy must both obey the development doctrine and contribute to overcome the shortcomings of the current business system. That is the number of low-performing enterprises, most of which are thin in the capital, weak in human resources, low in technology, brand value and weak in competitiveness, making the "center of the economy" yet enough to pull labor productivity up fast. The number of enterprises increased slowly, the number of enterprises had to stop operating highly, causing more stress on jobs, high social losses and wastes, and the living standard slowly improved ...

The main bottleneck that hinders the improvement of the number and quality of businesses, is that the economic institution, despite many recommendations and resolutions from 10-15 years ago, has not changed much. The Government exhorted, experts called for breakthrough solutions, but "breakthrough" could not "break" forever, because the "breakthrough" was too weak or too little, or because the machine was stagnant, did not do it (Nguyen Dinh Cung) , cited by Nguyen Tuyen, 2019). At the same time, it is necessary to improve the allocation of resources, balance the capital contribution for infrastructure upgrading with support for enterprise development, wisely attract FDI capital, and divest state capital from enterprises. It is accelerating the transformation of the growth model, strong development of small and medium-sized enterprises, meeting the "hunger" for technology and creativity, improving productivity (Investment Review, 2017). Encourage businesses to upgrade technology, increase their coordination, improve the distribution ...

Thirdly, developing digital infrastructure and e-government, promoting the development of technology enterprises and solutions for developing digital economy, improving the digital ecosystem to develop e-commerce and bringing digital business. into the principal activity of the business.

In parallel with the development of a strong national enterprise system, it is necessary to promote the expansion of the digital economy in order to develop digital businesses in enterprises. This challenge is not small, because according to the World Economic Forum (WEF), Vietnam's readiness to apply 4.0 technology is low, only in the preliminary group (CIEM, 2018a). Due to the widespread but unsafe digital infrastructure, it was among the top 3 countries with the most network attacks in 2018. In 2017, there were 10,000 attacks on Vietnam's Internet, causing 12 losses. , 3 trillion dongs (Nguyen Tham, 2018), users often suffer from privacy breaches, leaks and unauthorized information exploitation. On the other hand, after more than 10 years of implementing e-Government, basically completing the connection and linking of document management systems of ministries, branches and localities with the Government Office, ranked 6th in the ASEAN. Lack and form of making innovation start-up environment still have many shortcomings, from political institutions,

components, target groups, actors to guidelines and policies (Le Quoc Anh et al, 2018a) , curb, digital challenge business. Meanwhile, many development resources of the digital economy are "neglected", causing great waste, such as the scale of B2C e-commerce

Attention should be paid to the development of modern and safe digital infrastructure; build a standard and class e-government; promote the development of technology enterprises to ensure internal strength; implement practical and feasible solutions for digital economy development. Gradually improve the digital ecosystem to develop e-commerce, create attraction and coercion, doing digital business a key activity of the business.

Fourthly, reform education and training towards developing creative capacity and skills of learners, while increasing investment in research and development and innovation of digital ecosystems to gradually increase the efficiency of learners. business number.

Even though the basic "need" is sufficient, the digital business of the business will not be able to perform well if there is a shortage of qualified human resources; It is difficult to make a breakthrough when research and development (R&D) activities are not focused. For a digital business, businesses need human resources rich in creative ideas, especially in the department of digital business implementation and management. Therefore, it must be "revolutionary" in terms of education of the institute, "cramming", memorizing words, but far from reality, heavy theory lacking practice, restraining the value of human capital ... Therefore , we have to deepen reform of education and training, help form a dynamic, creative generation of young people, accepting destructive-creativity, dissatisfied with reality. We need to reduce the work to prove that we are doing right and lack the "breath" of life; pay more attention to the application of technology, be responsible for sharing economy and serving the community. China has succeeded in part because of the 1978 reform, which has depoliticized and commercialized higher education, in order to create a world-class entrepreneurial team (Vu Minh Khuong, 2013, p. 49). . As for us, the three best universities ranked 1,090, 1,355 and 2,241 in the first Webometrics rankings in 2019. On the other hand, it is necessary to increase the teaching of information technology and communication, along with the trends. new technology directions; the link between professional training institutions and businesses to provide a quality practice environment invest in research, quickly approach science and technology trends in the fields of new materials, new energy, digital, automation, artificial intelligence ... Building strong research groups and institutes Advanced research, centers of excellence in key areas of Industry 4.0 and having strategies and solutions to develop automation industries integrated with high technology such as information technology, intelligent supply chains, using new intellectual property management systems, optimizing business models. business ... - to gradually increase the size and efficiency of digital business.

Fifthly, exploit the spillover effects of FDI enterprises, from foreign partners, mobilize support from ministries, scientific circles, technology and the community to bring businesses' digital business. gradually go into methodical and effective operation.

Changing the mindset, the way business has been stable over the years, even through generations of people, is not easy, so it needs outside impact and support. Therefore, in order to develop digital business in enterprises, it is necessary to spread the new business methods, from partners, such as from FDI enterprises, from foreign enterprises in the same FTAs. Because Vietnamese enterprises are difficult to refuse when they enjoy the same "cake" of goods export in 2018 reached US \$ 243.48 billion - 70.4% of which value belongs to FDI enterprises. Or as the potential scale of Vietnam's logistics industry reaches 37-40 billion USD, equivalent to 25% of GDP in 2016, but only contributes 3% to the national GDP (Xuan Thu, 2017). Vietnamese businesses must account for only 10% of the value of logistics costs for domestically circulated goods and 40% for international purchases (Le Quoc Anh et al, 2018c). Therefore, Vietnamese enterprises should learn to do as they do, use digital business to work with them, gradually collecting what should be in Vietnam. To do this, in addition to the efforts of the business, need support from ministries, sectors, or from the science, technology and community. Need to help them with their conditions, environment, solutions, experience and problem solving;

help with scientific foundations, development theories, and relevant international experiences. Supporting industries, such as banking, education and training, commerce, and services, help them according to their capabilities and fields, for the common good. The social community helps to consume products, although the quality and safety are not up to the level of foreign products, to solve the output, when the oversupply situation is prevalent in the world. Moreover, in Vietnam, over the past few years, final consumption has often contributed to over 70% of GDP growth. Therefore, it will contribute greatly to help the digital business activities of the enterprise quickly overcome the difficult and startling period, gradually go into order, order and development

6. Conclusion

Developing a digital business is an important and urgent task of Vietnamese enterprises, demonstrating the efforts of businessmen in our country to overcome the limitations and weaknesses left behind by history. That development is actually a Vietnamese people making the digital transformation process inevitable faster, with a clearer orientation, to serve the common development process better. Thereby, it brings not only practical benefits for each enterprise, for clusters and chains, but also for the entire business system, for the whole economy, and for the society in general. And although this work has made many achievements, it is still not limited, weak, but to promote faster and stronger is not easy. By the side of the bottlenecks, such as the wide coverage of digital infrastructure but not high quality, lack of necessary human resources, lack of investment capital, or the ability of businesses. Our country still has many invisible bottlenecks, such as Still using the development doctrine and growth model of dozens of years ago, to subsidy thinking dominates the management of the market economy. More ominous is that they know wrong but slow to fix, know that errors indifferently, emotionless before the lag of the nation, bladder before the difficulties of the business. The pillars of Industry 4.0 such as the Ministry of Information and Communications, Education and Training, Ministry of Science and Technology have not pioneered the reform to enter the digital economy Luckily, there are ripples. Meanwhile, digital business development has many opportunities and motivations, from the Party's timely leadership through Resolution No. 52-NQ / TW, the National Assembly's support through the Law on Small Business Support and medium, the direction of the Government accompanies enterprises. On the other hand, with the hidden power of the business system, with the determination of the businessmen, the contribution of science and technology, the community's contribution. Along with the emergence and development of the Vietnam Digital Communications Association (VDCA), Vietnam Digital Agriculture Association (VIDA), efforts to turn 2019 into a digital business year of enterprises Regarding the digital business of Vietnamese enterprises, there have been many strides, to both integrate more successfully in the era of globalization, and contribute to narrowing the development gap between Vietnam and the great powers ..

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